

A linear tablature for ukulele transcription

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Abstract

A new tablature shorthand notation for ukulele transcription is proposed.

Keywords— tablature; ukulele; transcription

1 Motivation

In ukulele transcription, due to the limited extension of the instrument, the attempt to extend the space available for the leading voice may result in moving the other voices (bass line and possible intermediate voices) out of their original range. This has consequences in terms of voice crossing, possible blurring of the leading voice and/or of other melodic lines, hampered melodic continuity, loss of the original salience of single notes or of sequence of notes.

In [3] the use of top-down arpeggios has been proposed in order to overcome some of these drawbacks ¹. The shorthand notation for ukulele tablature proposed in the present work, which should be read as an appendix to [3], is deemed to provide a simple representation for those arpeggios. This tablature is specifically thought for high-G ukulele - whose players more frequently face the above-mentioned problems - and is intended as a shorthand notation, to be possibly annotated in a single line under the original score. ²

2 Linear tablature

As in standard tablature, also in linear tablature the fret on which to put the finger is indicated by a number, but - lacking the four bars frame - the string is identified by one of the symbols $\text{—} \backslash | /$ i.e.:

$$\begin{array}{lcl} / & = & A_4 \\ | & = & E_4 \\ \backslash & = & C_4 \\ \text{—} & = & G_4 \end{array}$$

For open strings no number is indicated after the string symbol. Colon, semicolon, full stop, comma and quotation mark (: . , ") are used to indicate duration to the next note; so duration symbols do not necessarily indicate the length of the note: ³

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¹Due to re-entrant tuning, the order of the notes in the arpeggios can be different from the order in which the strings are played.

²For an introduction to a more standard tablature, as well as for an excellent handbook on ukulele see [5].

³This is not different from other types of tablatures, see [1, p.54], [4], [2]

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$_2/3.$ $13/2.$ $_211/.$ $1.$ $_2/3.$ $_2$ $/3,$ $1\ _1/2.$ $_211.$ $1/2.$ $_1.$ $_2/:$

11

$11.$ $_2.$ $_1.$ $_3.$ $_2/.$ $12.$ $_13/1.$ $_2.$ $11/.$ $11\ 2.$ $_1.$ $/3.$

14

$_2/2.$ $11/.$ $_3.$ $11\ 2.$ $1/3.$ $/2.$ $_211.$ $1.$ $11/.$ $11/3.$ $11/.$

17

$_1.$ $_1.$ $11/.$ $_4\ 2\ 1\ 1.$ $_2\ 1/.$ $_4\ 2\ 1\ 1.$ $_4\ 1\ 3.$ $_2.$ $_2\ 1.$ $_1.$ $_2:$

2.2 Concise linear tablature

In handwriting, as a more concise alternative, the fret numbers can be written on the string symbol in Roman numerals as in the diagram below:

The tablature of *Poi che sei* would be like this:

♪ ♯ : Ⅱ \ | : ♯ / . \ | _ . \ | _ . ♯ / : \ | _ . ♪ ♯ . Ⅱ \ | . ♪ ♯ :
 Ⅱ \ | . \ | . ♪ ♯ . / | \ . _ ♪ ♯ . ♯ / . | _ . ♪ ♯ ♯ . _ | . ♯ \ | . Ⅱ ♪ ♯ .
 Ⅱ | ♯ . ♯ ♯ . ♪ ♯ / . / . Ⅱ | ♯ . Ⅱ ♯ ♯ | Ⅱ ♯ . Ⅱ ♯ . | ♯ . Ⅱ . Ⅱ / :
 ♯ . Ⅱ . \ . _ ♯ . ♪ / . ♯ . _ ♯ ♯ . ♯ / . ♯ \ | \ . ♯ .
 ♪ ♯ . ♯ / . \ | ♯ . ♯ Ⅱ . | _ ♯ . ♯ . ♪ ♯ / . ♯ \ . ♯ ♯ . ♯ / .
 \ . | _ . ♯ / . Ⅱ ♪ ♯ . Ⅱ \ | . Ⅱ ♪ ♯ . _ ♯ ♯ . _ ♯ . Ⅱ | . \ . ♯ :

References

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Poi che sei

da IL SECONDO LIBRO DELLE VILLANELLE

alla Napolitana a Tre Voci de Diversi Musici di Barri; raccolte per Ioanne de Antiquis (Venezia 1574)

Anonymous

The musical score for 'Poi che sei' is presented in three systems, each with three staves. The first system (measures 1-7) begins with a treble clef and a common time signature (C). The melody is primarily composed of quarter and eighth notes. The second system (measures 8-13) starts with a measure rest and continues with a similar melodic line. The third system (measures 14-20) also begins with a measure rest and concludes the piece. The notation includes various rhythmic values and accidentals, such as sharps and a flat, across the three staves.